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Experimental campaign for the characterization of precipitation in a complex terrain site using high resolution observations

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Abstract. Precipitation has an effect on wind power at several levels. It affects the wind current, blade status, wake development and power production. Power production is affected by the harmful effect of precipitation on the blades eroding its surface and altering their aerodynamic performance. In the past decades, wind has been characterized using different techniques, but less effort has been devoted to precipitation measurement. In this work, the results of an experimental campaign performed at a high altitude complex terrain site to characterize precipitation using high resolution observations are presented. The campaign, carried out at CENER's experimental wind farm (Alaiz) during 2023 within the framework of the Horizon Europe AIRE project, lasted nine months and different precipitation types (rain, snow, graupel) were recorded using a Micro Rain Radar (MRR), a Parsivel disdrometer and a rain gauge co-located with an instrumented wind mast with anemometers and wind vanes at different heights. Two case studies are selected to illustrate the wide range of variability found in precipitation conditions, particularly during the cool season. Precipitation characterization is very challenging at high temporal resolution, making necessary measurement campaigns with different precipitation equipment to optimize their performance and optimise its calibration. The study of precipitation profiles with MRR will support the study of precipitation impingement on wind turbine blades responsible of blade erosion. Moreover, these measurements will contribute to create the link between in-field wind farm data, laboratory experiments in rain erosion test rig and blade damage models necessary to improve wind turbine and wind farm design and operation.

1. Introduction

Currently, wind turbines and wind farms are designed using the assessment of Annual Energy Production (AEP) and turbine loads, applying models and tools that are based on standard wind conditions. Wind farm developers use several models and tools to optimize the wind turbine and wind farm design, to define the maintenance plan, and to calculate the return on the investment. However, these models do not take into account the physics and aerodynamics of atmospheric wind flows at high altitudes and complex terrains. In addition, the existing tools do not consider

climate effects, such as precipitation and sand, on the design, durability, and performance of wind turbines and wind farms at differing locations. Furthermore, the availability of high temporal resolution rain data, global irradiance and materials degradation characteristics used on leading edge protection systems design is scarce, which limits the validation of the models.

One of the most important effects of precipitation on wind turbines is blade erosion [1]. With blade tip speeds reaching up to 110 m/s [2], the repeated impact of raindrops or airborne particles is sufficiently energetic to reduce the expected lifetime of blade materials. Rain droplets hit the wind turbine blades and erode their surface, leading to important performance losses and increased costly maintenance operations [3, 4]. The performance losses due to blade erosion are difficult to be measured on the field. Some experimental [5] and numerical [6] studies report AEP losses of about 4%, which might be increased up to 6% when related to loss of top coat on the leading edge [2]. The understanding of precipitation characteristics, such as droplet size and distribution, velocity and type of precipitation, is necessary to develop blade damage models and control strategies that help to reduce the operation and maintenance costs caused by blade erosion on wind turbines.

In this work, results of an experimental campaign performed at a high altitude complex terrain site to characterize precipitation using high resolution equipment are presented. The campaign, carried out at CENER's experimental wind farm (Alaiz N Spain) during 2023, lasted nine months and different precipitation types (rain, snow, graupel) were recorded using a Micro Rain Radar, a Parsivel disdrometer and a rain gauge co-located with an instrumented wind mast with anemometers and wind vanes at different heights. These measurements will contribute to understand precipitation characteristics to be used in wind turbine and wind farm design and to create the link between in-field wind farm data, laboratory experiments in rain erosion test rig and blade damage models.

2. AIRE Project

The measurement campaign is performed under the scope of the Horizon Europe AIRE project. One of its main objectives is to study the atmospheric flow aerodynamics effect over wind farms, wind turbines and its components [7]. The project started with precipitation, airborne particles and wind measurements at eight wind farms located in Europe. The work presented is part of one of the campaigns that are performed inside the project. All the data sets will be made public in an open access knowledge hub and will be used to create and optimize current tools and models that will help wind turbine owners and manufactures to design and control wind turbines and wind farms when they operate in climate conditions and sites more challenging than the standard ones.

3. Methodology

3.1. CENER's experimental wind farm

CENER's experimental wind farm is located at a high altitude (elevation 1,100 m) in a complex terrain 15 km SSE from Pamplona (Navarre, Spain). The size of the farm is 30 km x 30 km, and is suitable for the study of high-resolution mesoscale-to-microscale models with strong coupling between terrain and thermal stratification [8]. The prevailing wind directions are from the north and from the south. To the north of the wind farm there is a large valley at an elevation of around 700 m. To the south, the terrain is complex with the presence of some wind farms; the closest one is situated 2 km south.

The wind farm has four reference met masts (MP1, MP3, MP5 and MP6), each 118 m tall, situated at the north of six wind turbine positions (WT1 to WT6), where multi-megawatt wind turbines are installed for experimental purposes (Figure 1). Wind vanes and cup anemometers are attached to the met mast at heights between 40 m and 118 m above ground level (AGL) to measure wind speed and wind direction. Temperature and relative humidity are measured at

97 m or 113 m AGL, depending on the mast. A pyranometer installed at 5 m AGL on MP6 records the global irradiance.

Figure 1. Alaiz 3-D profile (left), met mast and wind turbine distribution (top-right), MRR and disdrometer located by the MP6 (bottom-right).

3.2. Equipment for measuring precipitation

For the characterization of precipitation, a pluviometer (tipping bucket rain gauge), a disdrometer (model Parsivel2, hereafter Parsivel), and a Micro Rain Radar (model MRR-Pro, hereafter MRR) were used. The instruments are shown in Figure 1 bottom-right. The equipment is installed at ground level (elevation 1115 m) at 16 m west of MP6 to avoid interference of MRR's signals with the met mast. Parsivel is a laser disdrometer, manufactured by OTT Hydromet GmbH, widely used for microphysical precipitation studies [9]. It allows to record fall speed and size spectra of precipitation particles stored in 32 x 32 classes, here recorded at 1 minute temporal resolution. The instrument computes a number of derived variables such as rainfall rate (R), radar reflectivity (Z), kinetic energy of the particles (KE) and identifies the precipitation type. They can be used to obtain statistical relationships from local measurements, for example Z-R or KE-R ([10, 11]), which can be later employed to derive R from weather radar measurements or KE from rain gauge records. This fact makes disdrometers very valuable equipment for the characterization of precipitation.

Moreover, Parsivel provides the precipitation type in different standard formats used at SYNOP weather reports or METAR observations defined by the World Meteorological Organization [12], including the following eight classes: 1) drizzle, 2) rain, 3) rain and drizzle, 4) snow with rain and/or drizzle, 5) snow, 6) snow grains, 7) soft hail -also called graupel- and 8) hail. Precipitation type is an important feature of precipitation for many applications, for example when there are cold season thunderstorms or storms with transitions from liquid to solid precipitation [13, 14, 15].

MRR is a vertically pointing K band frequency modulated continuous wave Doppler radar [16], manufactured by Metek GmbH. The unit used here is configured to sample 128 height gates with 25 m vertical resolution (i.e. covering from 0 m to 3,200 m AGL) and 64 spectral Doppler

bins at each height with a temporal resolution of 5 s. This setting provides a good description of precipitation profile characteristics, for example allowing to distinguish typical radar patterns characteristic of stratiform or convective precipitation [17, 18]. The MRR data acquisition software allows to record raw spectral data and also derived variables from Doppler moments such as fall velocity (W) and equivalent radar reflectivity (Z_e), i.e. radar reflectivity computed assuming liquid precipitation observed under Rayleigh scattering. The study of precipitation with MRR to obtain vertical profiles will be very valuable to understand the precipitation impingement on wind turbine blades and to optimize the calibration of other precipitation equipment.

The data sets collected during the experimental campaign will allow an exhaustive description of precipitation to be used to create and optimize models and tools used currently to wind turbine and wind farm design. In the following subsections it is illustrated specifically the use of MRR and Parsivel data to characterize precipitation features during the field campaign.

3.3. MRR data postprocessing

MRR spectral raw data is post-processed with the RaProM-Pro software, which computes Doppler moments and derived variables such as a simplified hydrometeor classification (i.e. distinguishing precipitation types such as snow or rain) or radar bright-band detection, which facilitates the data analysis (more information and public access to this post-processing software can be found in [15, 17, 19]). Classification of the precipitation type is an essential aspect here as it allows to separate liquid from solid precipitation, given that erosivity of rainfall is computed from particle size distributions identified as rain drops, from which kinetic energy is calculated given their terminal velocity [20, 11, 21]. Moreover, the application of RaProM-Pro also allows to provide the frequency of occurrence of different precipitation types, which is also relevant to study the impact of precipitation on wind turbines.

3.4. Precipitation erosivity

Rainfall erosion studies have been carried out to characterize the capacity of raindrop kinetic energy, or erosivity, to detach soil particles by direct impact. The total detached soil mass is the result of the product of rainfall erosivity and soil erodibility, which describes the characteristics of a specific soil type [22, 23, 21]. Precise KE measurements require raindrop size and fall speed spectra, which have been provided for decades by disdrometers [11, 21]. The KE was calculated as the sum of all individual raindrop kinetic energies, explicitly computed from their diameters and speeds, variables obtained from disdrometer observations; R is calculated in a similar way as described in [10, 11]. Frequently used equations to relate KE and R are $KE/R = c_1 + c_2 \log R$ ([22]) or $KE/R = c_3(1 - c_4)e^{-c_5 R}$ ([23]), where c_1 , c_2 , c_3 , c_4 , and c_5 are constants.

Unlike traditional erosivity studies of soil detachment, to assess the potential erosion damage on wind turbine blades, wind measurements and blade speeds must be used to estimate the precipitation particle relative speed to the blade, a computation which will be done in next steps of the AIRE project. In this paper, erosivity estimates presented in the results section consider disdrometric data.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Overview

The analysis of Parsivel observations indicate that from 17 February to 16 November 2023, 3514.1 hours were recorded. Out of them, 251.5 hours contained precipitation, including 14.1 hours of drizzle, 70.5 hours of drizzle with rain, 136.2 hours of rain, 20.9 hours of snow, 8.1 hours of soft hail, 7 minutes of hail and no records of snow grains. This is a valuable data set as it contains substantial cases of liquid, solid, and also mixed precipitation, which has been characterized for the first time at CENER's experimental wind farm. The results will help

wind turbine manufactures and wind farm owners to understand the drivers of blade erosion in complex terrain, high altitude sites with precipitation characteristics similar to the ones in Alaiz wind farm. Furthermore, the obtained results combined with the data recorded from the met masts will be used on the construction of a blade erosion risk atlas for a reference wind turbine (this will be done in subsequent parts of the project and is aligned to the objectives of IEA Task 46 Erosion of Wind Turbine [24]).

4.2. Case studies

A few cases observed during the campaign presented transitions of different precipitation types at ground level. Two of them were selected for this study. Figure 2 shows MRR observations of equivalent radar reflectivity Z_e , vertical fall velocity W and estimated precipitation type on 23 February 2023, presenting a transition from liquid to solid precipitation at ground level. Note that Parsivel observations, included at the lowest level of each panel, are consistent with MRR estimates, particularly those close to the ground. Figure 3 shows another event with precipitation transitions, in this case including graupel, rain, hail and snow. Overall agreement of hydrometeor types classified at the lowest MRR height available (from 75 to 100 m AGL) compared to Parsivel observations in the two cases presented is illustrated by the similar proportions of the main pure precipitation types found (excluding hail and mixed solid and liquid precipitation). Precipitation proportions estimated by the MRR for snow, rain and graupel were 52%, 7% and 14%, respectively, and by the Parsivel, 37%, 11% and 37%. These discrepancies can be explained by microphysical changes on the precipitation particles falling to the ground, such as the melting of snowflakes being transformed into raindrops, and by the differences in the classification of hydrometeors, particularly those present in minor proportions.

Particle size distributions for the different precipitation types observed at ground level by the Parsivel disdrometer during these events exhibit a wide range of values (see Figure 4). These distributions can typically be modelled with a unimodal right skewed distribution function such as the gamma distribution [10, 11] describing a relatively high increase in the concentration of small particles where the maximum concentration (mode) is found and then a more gentle decrease to larger particle concentrations. Note that despite the number of large particles can be much lower than the number of medium and smaller particles, the former can have a dominant effect regarding their kinetic energy, given the fact that the particle fall speed increases with size.

The cases shown here, including different solid precipitation types and frequent transitions (e.g. from rain to snow, then to rain, etc.), illustrate well the challenges involved in the characterization of precipitation at high temporal resolution. Moreover, this introduces further difficulties in the calculation of kinetic energy as higher uncertainties are due to variability of solid precipitation particles type and density.

4.3. Kinetic Energy

A estimation of kinetic energy derived from Parsivel data is presented here. Firstly, based on 13,243 1-minute liquid precipitation records, a filter was applied considering rainfall rates above 0.05 mm/h and a minimum of 26 precipitation particles to include a minimum erosivity effect, resulting in 11,135 1-minute records. Next, the two fitting functions of KE/R described in Figure 5 were obtained. Both fitting functions provided equivalent Root Mean Square Errors ($3.79 \text{ J m}^{-2} \text{ mm}^{-1}$ equivalent to about 25% of the mean value) when compared to the original KE values. As it can be seen in the right panel of Figure 5, rainfall rates are mostly below 10 mm h^{-1} so higher sample densities are found on this area (representing 97.2% of the samples), which obviously influences the behaviour of the fitting function. The two obtained fitting lines capture reasonably well the increase of KE/R with R at low R values (here below 3 mm h^{-1}) and have

been used to characterize the average local characteristics of rainfall erosivity. However, they are of limited use for specific events considering the high variability of KE/R at short time scale.

Furthermore, based on the same disdrometric dataset of liquid precipitation, two additional relationships between KE and R , and KE and Z were explored (Figure 6), similar to the classical Z - R relationships between radar reflectivity and rainfall rate. According to the Pearson correlation coefficient obtained for the fitted functions with the data sets, these relationships could be employed to estimate KE using habitual meteorological equipment, such as pluviometer, instead of disdrometers or MRR.

Figure 2. MRR and Parsivel observations, on 23 February 2023 from 1:45 to 3:45 UTC, of equivalent radar reflectivity Z_e (top), vertical fall velocity W (middle) and estimated precipitation type (bottom). Parsivel observations are shown at the lowest level of each panel using the same colour scale as MRR data.

Figure 3. MRR and Parsivel observations, on 1 April 2023 from 22:30 to 23:59 UTC, of equivalent radar reflectivity Z_e (top), vertical fall velocity W (middle) and estimated precipitation type (bottom). Parsivel observations are shown at the lowest level of each panel using the same colour scale as MRR data.

Figure 4. Particle size distribution $N(D)$ for different precipitation types observed by the Parsivel disdrometer at ground level on 23 February 2023 from 1:45 to 3:45 UTC (left) and 1 April 2023 from 22:30 to 23:59 UTC (right).

Figure 5. Kinetic Energy divided by Rainfall Rate (KE/R) vs Rainfall Rate (R) scatter density plot and fitted functions using Alaiz campaign in 2023 11,135 1-minute ground-level liquid disdrometer records. The right panel shows a zoom of the black rectangle in the left panel. Shaded colors indicate sample density.

5. Conclusions

This paper provides an overview of the results of a field campaign carried out at a high altitude and complex terrain experimental wind farm focused on the advanced characterization of the precipitation. This work will be used to improve models and tools used for wind turbine and wind farm design and optimization. The study was performed during nine months using high resolution equipment (i.e. MRR and disdrometer). It was determined that most of the precipitation was rain (221 h), followed by snow (20.9 h) and hail (8.1 h of soft hail and 7 minutes of hail). Work is under way to complete the analysis of the data sets obtained, including

Figure 6. Kinetic Energy (KE) vs Rainfall Rate (R) (left), and Kinetic Energy (KE) vs Radar Reflectivity (Z) (right) scatter density plots and fitted functions with their Pearson correlation coefficient (r) obtained with Alaiz-2023 11,135 1-minute ground-level liquid disdrometer records. Shaded colors indicate sample density.

the comparison of MRR precipitation estimates with pluviometer and disdrometer records, which may lead to update the MRR calibration constant. Presented results, using MRR and disdrometer observations, illustrate the importance of adequately characterizing precipitation features, including precipitation type, prior to further analysis. Agreement of hydrometeor types classified at the lowest MRR height available compared to Parsivel observations in the two cases presented is found (excluding hail and mixed solid and liquid precipitation). In addition, fitting functions to the data sets are defined to estimate the kinetic energy that could be used to improve measurements with habitual meteorological equipment. Future work will be devoted to combine drop size distribution data and subsequent rainfall erosivity estimates from MRR data, wind data, and wind turbine rotation speed to assess their effect on wind turbine production and on lifetime of blade materials.

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